

Supporting Information

Light-responsive Biowaste-Derived and Bio-Inspired Textiles: Dancing Between Bio-Friendliness and Antibacterial Functionality

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Sup. Fig. 1. Standard curve for CCK-8 assay.

Establishment of the standard curve for the CCK-8-based method for quantification of viable bacteria on the textile samples:

A single *S. aureus* colony was transferred to 2 mL of liquid LB medium. The bacteria were aerobically grown for 5 hours at 37 °C at 175 rpm. The resulting suspension was diluted with LB medium at a 1:75 v/v ratio and incubated overnight at 37 °C under aerobic conditions on a rotary shaker at 175 rpm. The OD₆₀₀ of overnight culture was measured using LB medium as a blank. The overnight culture was serially diluted in LB medium to obtain bacteria suspensions with concentrations ranging from approximately 10³ to 10⁹ CFU/mL. The concentration of bacteria in the obtained suspensions was determined in triplicate by serial dilution method. Immediately after plating on agar, viable bacteria in each dilution of the overnight culture were quantified in triplicate using the CCK-8 method described in section 2.6.3. Each dilution was mixed with CCK-8 reagent at a 10:1 v/v ratio and incubated for 3 hours at 37 °C. The suspensions were centrifuged at 5500 rpm for 15 min. 110 µL aliquots of supernatants were transferred to a microtiter plate. The absorbance of the solutions was measured at 450 nm using a microplate reader. The average absorbance obtained for the blank samples was subtracted from the remaining absorbance readings. Concentrations of bacteria [CFU/mL] in the dilutions of the overnight culture were plotted against respective 450 nm absorbance values. The standard curve was established by linearly fitting the experimental data points.

The results in Sup. Fig. 1 demonstrates a strong linear relationship ($R^2 = 0.989$) between the cell concentrations determined through the serial dilution method and their corresponding absorbance values. The equation derived from the standard curve by fitting the experimental data points within a bacteria concentration range of 1.639×10^3 to 1.013×10^9 CFU/mL is

displayed in the figure. Using this equation and the 450 nm absorbance values, concentrations of bacteria grown on the textile specimens and in positive control samples were calculated.

Sup. Fig. 2. Effect of different ball milling conditions on the size and distribution of SCG particles.

Sup. Fig. 3. FT-IR spectra of the developed textiles in the 2500 cm⁻¹ to 3500 cm⁻¹ range.

Sup. Fig. 4. UV-Vis-NIR spectra of the photothermal agents: PDA and SCG.

UV-Vis-NIR analysis of photothermal agents

UV-Vis-NIR analyses in solid-state absorption mode were employed to investigate the absorption characteristics of PDA and SCG coatings. The coatings, with a thickness of 80 μm , were prepared by separate electro spraying of PDA (12% w/v in DMF) and SCG (12% w/v in ethanol) suspensions. Measurements were performed in the wavelength range of 350 to 900 nm at a rate of 1 nm per minute. Sup. Fig. 4 illustrates the UV-Vis-NIR absorption spectra of these photothermal agents. Both PDA and SCG exhibit relatively high absorption in the UV region, which decreases as the wavelength enters the visible and then the NIR I region. However, this decrease is more pronounced for SCG. A noteworthy observation is a minor peak at approximately 490 nm for PDA (marked with a red arrow), which corresponds to dopaminechrome, a structure in PDA that forms as the polymerization of PDA progresses.¹

Sup. Fig. 5. UV-Vis-NIR absorption spectra of the developed textiles: (a) PAN and (b) PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles in the range of 350 to 900 nm, close-up of (c) PAN and (d) PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles in the NIR I region (700 to 900 nm).

NIR absorbance of the developed textiles

The optical properties of the PAN, PAN/SCG, and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles were further evaluated using UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy in the solid state, in absorption mode, in the wavelength range from 350 to 900 nm, at a rate of 1 nm per minute, with a Perkin Elmer Lambda 1050+ (Madison, WI, USA) (Sup. Fig. 5). Since the photothermal properties of the textiles were evaluated with an 808 nm NIR laser, the absorption spectra in the NIR-I window (wavelength range from 700 to 900 nm) have been also reported in Sup. Fig. 5. It should be noted that the circular textiles, with a diameter of 9 mm and a thickness of 65 μm , used during UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy have the same mass of SCG (in the case of PAN/SCG, 0.5 mg of SCG) and PDA (in the case of (PAN/SCG)@PDA, 0.5 mg of SCG and 0.147 mg of PDA) as the textiles used during the evaluation of photothermal performance detailed in section 3.2 (Figure 3b and 3e).

A_{808} , the absorbance at 808 nm, is 0.003 for PAN, 0.208 for PAN/SCG, and 0.240 for (PAN/SCG)@PDA.

Photothermal conversion performance of the developed textiles

SCG microparticles in PAN/SCG and PDA in (PAN/SCG)@PDA enhance the photothermal properties of the developed micro-nanostructured textiles in this study. We extensively examined the temperature elevation of 200 μ L deionized water (DW) surrounding the developed textiles under irradiation by an 808 nm laser at varying power densities of 2.0, 2.5, and 3.0 W, as shown in Figures 3b and 3e.

The temperature rises dramatically within the first 600 seconds of irradiation. Minute temperature changes (ΔT) were observed for the next 600 seconds of irradiation until a steady-state temperature was reached. This phenomenon is attributed to fast heat loss at relatively high temperatures.

The photothermal conversion efficiency of PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA was measured using a method similar to those reported by Roper et al.² and Tian et al.³ The temperature change of the DW was recorded as a function of time under continuous irradiation, and ΔT was calculated according to the following equation:

$$\Delta T = T_{Max} - T_{Surr} \quad (1)$$

T_{max} is the equilibrium temperature, and T_{Surr} is the ambient temperature of the surroundings. Furthermore, when the irradiation source was shut off, the temperature decrease of the DW was monitored to determine the rate of heat transfer from the system to the environment. The photothermal conversion efficiency, η , can be calculated using the following equation:

$$\eta = \frac{hS(\Delta T) - Q_{Dis}}{I/A(1 - 10^{-A_{808}})} \quad (2)$$

Where h is the heat transfer coefficient, S is the surface area of the container, Q_{Dis} is the heat associated with the NIR-light absorbance of the solvent, I is incident laser power, A is the textile area (0.636 cm^2), and A_{808} is the absorbance of the textiles at a wavelength of 808 nm (Sup. Fig. 5).

The following equation should be considered to calculate the hS :

$$\tau = \frac{m_s C_s}{hS} \quad (3)$$

Where τ is the sample system time constant, m_s and C_s are the solvent's mass and heat capacity (i.e., DW).

The time constant function can be written as:

$$t = -\tau \ln(\theta) \quad (4)$$

Where t is the corresponding time from the cooling stage, and θ is a dimensionless driving force temperature and can be defined as:

$$\theta = \frac{T - T_{Surr}}{\Delta T} \quad (5)$$

T is the real-time temperature during the cooling stage. The time constant for heat transfer from the system can be determined by applying the linear time data from the cooling period versus the negative natural logarithm of driving force temperature. Sup. Fig. 6 shows representative linear data fit for PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles after shutting off the NIR laser with a power of 2.5 W.

Sup. Fig. 6. Determining the time constant for heat transfer from the system by applying the linear time data from the cooling period versus the negative natural logarithm of driving force temperature; (a) (PAN/SCG)@PDA and (b) PAN/SCG (obtained from the cooling stage of Figures 3b and 3e, NIR laser power 2.5 W).

Additionally, the mass m_s is 0.2 g, and the specific heat capacity C_s is 4.2 J/g. Thus, according to Equation 3, the heat transfer coefficient, hS , can be obtained. Q_{Dis} , which expresses heat dissipated from light absorbed by the DW, was measured independently to be 8.4 mW using the same setup containing pure DW without the presence of textiles. Substituting these values into Equation 2, the 808 nm laser heat conversion efficiency of PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles can be calculated. Table S1 presents the recorded values of ΔT , the hS , and the photothermal conversion efficiency for PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles.

Table S1: The ΔT and hS of DW, as well as the η of PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles, under irradiation by an 808 nm laser at varying power densities.

		Laser power		
		2.0 W	2.5 W	3.0 W
PAN/SCG	ΔT ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	26	31	33
	hS ($\text{mW}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	4.33	4.42	4.41
	η (%)	21.58	21.29	18.91
(PAN/SCG)@PDA	ΔT ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	43	48	53
	hS ($\text{mW}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	4.68	5.68	5.73
	η (%)	35.8	39.2	36.5

The average photothermal conversion efficiency of PAN/SCG textiles, calculated across the three laser power densities (2.0 W, 2.5 W, and 3.0 W), was found to be $20.60 \pm 0.85\%$. The error margin represents the standard error of the mean. For (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles, the average photothermal conversion efficiency was similarly determined to be $37.19 \pm 1.03\%$, showing enhanced performance due to the presence of PDA coating.

Although the calculation of η indirectly accounts for the concentration of the photothermal agent (as A_{808} depends on the concentration, or in our case, the mass of the photothermal agent), it is independent of the rate at which the water temperature rises during irradiation.

Photothermal Mechanism and Efficiency of Melanin-like Materials (MLM)

Melanin-like materials (MLM) are versatile compounds with many technological applications due to their physical and chemical properties combined with their inherent biocompatibility.⁴ An example of MLM is melanoidins, the Maillard-reaction products naturally occurring during food cooking. They can also be produced during thermal pretreatment of organic solid waste or sewage sludges, but their recovery and purification are still under investigation.⁵ Coffee is rich in melanoidins.⁶ During the brewing process, a portion of these organic compounds remains in the SCGs. Melanoidins are known for their characteristic brown pigmentation and exhibit a broad absorption spectrum extending from UV to NIR wavelengths.⁷ This optical property signifies their potential for applications harnessing light-based therapies. Studies on melanoidins derived from diverse sources, including coffee, beer, and sweet wine, reveal that molecular weight influences their absorption characteristics.⁸ Higher molecular weight melanoidins demonstrate enhanced light absorption and, consequently, stronger photoacoustic signals. The presence of aromatic rings within melanoidin structures suggests that a conjugation effect underpins their photothermal mechanism.⁹ Upon light exposure, electrons within these aromatic systems transition to an excited π^* orbital. As these excited electrons relax back to the ground state, a portion of the absorbed energy dissipates as heat. This non-radiative relaxation pathway contributes to the photothermal conversion property of melanoidins, making them intriguing candidates for photothermal applications.

PDA is another MLM¹⁰ and, similar to natural melanin, has a broad optical absorption and efficient non-radiative decay, which gives it an intrinsic photothermal property. Melanin's complex chemical structure, composed of disordered indolic and phenolic units, enables it to absorb a wide range of wavelengths across the UV-Vis-NIR spectrum.^{11,12} This broadband absorption provides a basis for MLM ability to harness light energy across multiple wavelengths. Upon light absorption, the excited electrons within MLM rapidly relax back to their ground state. Crucially, this relaxation process occurs primarily through non-radiative pathways, where the absorbed energy is dissipated as heat rather than re-emitted as light

(fluorescence).¹³ This inefficient fluorescence, combined with the broad absorption, results in highly effective photon-to-heat conversion.

Sup. Fig. 7. Temporal profiles of dry PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles showing their temperature increase from room temperature when subjected to 2.5 W of NIR laser power.

Sup. Fig. 8. Qualitative viability of L929 fibroblast cells seeded on (SCG/PAN)@PDA, SCG/PAN, and TCP performed at days 3 and 7 of incubation. Green indicates live cells, whereas red represents dead cells. Scale bars: 100 μ m.

Sup. Fig. 9. Confocal images of cells seeded on (SCG/PAN)@PDA, SCG/PAN, TCP and stained with Actin (green color) for cell cytoskeleton visualization and DAPI (blue color) for individuating the cell nuclei. Scale bar: 100 μm .

Sup. Fig. 10. SEM images of cell spreading on (SCG/PAN)@PDA, SCG/PAN textiles, and TCP performed on days 3 and 7 of culture.

Sup. Fig. 11. Temporal profiles of the PAN/SCG and (PAN/SCG)@PDA textiles immersed in 200 μ L of LB medium irradiated with a 2.5 W NIR laser.

Sup. Fig. 12. SEM images of PAN/SCG textile cultured with *S. aureus* showing two locations before and after irradiation with NIR laser.

References in Supporting information

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